

EXPLORATION OF BURNOUT PHENOMENA AND COPING STRATEGIES FOR WORK-RELATED STRESS AMONG GENERATION Z

Ni Putu Shintania Pramesti¹, Luh Putu Mahyuni²

Master of Management Study Program, Faculty of Business Economics, Universitas Pendidikan Nasional

E-mail: shintaniia018@gmail.com

Received : 25 January 2026

Accepted : 25 February 2026

Revised : 01 February 2026

Published : 09 March 2026

Abstract

This study aims to explore the phenomenon of burnout and coping strategies in dealing with work stress among Generation Z (Gen Z) during the high season. This phenomenon arises due to the increasing workload, multiple tasks, and excessive working hours experienced by Gen Z workers. With the unique characteristics of Gen Z such as the need for work-life balance and sensitivity to mental health, this can trigger burnout. The study used a qualitative approach with an exploratory design. Data were collected through in-depth interviews with Gen Z workers, coworkers, and management, and supported by operational documentation. The results showed that work stress was triggered by organizational factors, such as increasing task demands, dual roles, time pressure, limited organizational structure, and interpersonal relationship dynamics. Continuous stressful conditions can lead to burnout, which is characterized by physical, emotional, and mental exhaustion, as well as low self-achievement. To deal with this pressure, Gen Z workers apply coping strategies such as social support, self-healing, and self-evaluation. These findings underscore the importance of organizations' role in creating a supportive and adaptive work environment to Gen Z characteristics to prevent work stress and burnout, particularly in the small to medium-scale tourism sector.

Keywords: *Burnout, Work Stress, Gen Z, Coping Strategy.*

INTRODUCTION

The tourism sector plays a vital role as a major source of foreign exchange earnings and as a driver of national economic growth, particularly in reducing unemployment and increasing a country's productivity (Yakup, 2019). In Bali, tourism is one of the primary engines of the local economy, especially in Ubud, an area renowned for its natural and cultural attractions. In Ubud, Bali, many Generation Z workers are employed in the tourism industry, including restaurants, hotels, and villas. This distinctive characteristic makes Ubud one of Bali's leading tourist destinations, experiencing a significant increase in visitor arrivals each year, particularly during the year-end holiday season. One example is D'Carik Villas Ubud, a villa located in a rural area of Ubud, Bali, specifically in Gentong Village, Tegalalang, Gianyar. The term "D'Carik" means "in the rice field," reflecting the natural atmosphere and tranquility offered by the property, which is surrounded by green rice paddies, scenic landscapes, and a serene rural environment. D'Carik Villas Ubud experiences a surge in tourist visits during the high season, with occupancy rates reaching 23–26 nights per month per villa unit, directly affecting employees' work intensity. The increase in tourist numbers leads to a heavier workload for employees, particularly younger workers from Generation Z who serve in frontline roles such as housekeeping, front office, food and beverage (F&B), and marketing. These employees are often required to perform multiple roles (double job descriptions), work overtime, and operate under high pressure to maintain service performance for guests. The distinctive characteristics of Gen Z compared to previous generations in interpreting work also create implications for organizations in managing human resources aligned with Gen Z expectations to ensure business sustainability (Agarwal & Vaghela, 2019).

EXPLORATION OF BURNOUT PHENOMENA AND COPING STRATEGIES FOR WORK-RELATED STRESS AMONG GENERATION Z

Ni Putu Shintania Pramesti and Luh Putu Mahyuni

Figure 1. BPD Data of Bali Prov. 2024

According to Badan Pusat Statistik Provinsi Bali, the number of international tourists arriving directly in Bali in December 2024 reached 551,100 visits. This figure represents a 16.54% increase compared to November 2024, which recorded 472,900 visits. The increase occurred because December is a global Christmas and New Year holiday period, as well as a time of school holidays and collective leave in Indonesia. As a premier tourist destination, Bali offers a tropical climate, unique local culture, and various year-end events that attract visitors. Tourists from Australia dominated arrivals in December 2024, accounting for 24.78% of total visits. The room occupancy rate of star-rated hotels in December 2024 was recorded at 63.71%, an increase of 4.10 percentage points compared to November 2024 (BPS Bali, 2024). This surge in tourist arrivals increases workload across the tourism sector, particularly in workplaces with small team structures but substantial responsibilities, such as D’Carik Villas Ubud during the high season. Without adequate organizational support, this condition has the potential to generate work-related stress.

Figure 2. Gen Z Resignation Data 2023

Data from GoodStats (2023) indicate that 56.9% of Gen Z employees resign due to work stress caused by excessive working hours, 41.8% due to heavy workloads, and 37.2% due to a lack of work–life balance. These findings suggest that burnout is no longer viewed merely as an individual issue but as a serious organizational concern that can lead to high turnover if left unaddressed. Generation Z, born between 1997 and 2012, is now beginning to dominate the workforce in Indonesia. This generation has distinctive characteristics, including a strong emphasis on mental health, high expectations regarding work–life balance, and a tendency to change jobs quickly if dissatisfied with the work environment (GoodStats, 2023). Gen Z also experiences higher levels of anxiety, stress, and burnout compared to previous generations such as Generation X or Millennials. This is supported by a report from the American Psychological Association (2020), which identifies Gen Z as the age group most vulnerable to mental pressure due to work factors, future uncertainty, and high social expectations.

Work stress is one of the primary triggers of psychological disturbances in the workplace, especially among younger workers such as Gen Z (Suartana, 2020). It can originate from various sources, including excessive workload, role ambiguity, interpersonal conflict, and authoritarian leadership styles within organizations (Shandy et al., 2013). If not managed effectively, work stress can lead to burnout—a condition characterized by profound physical, emotional, and mental exhaustion resulting from prolonged workplace pressure (Maslach & Leiter, 2016). Burnout not only reduces employee productivity but also negatively affects psychological health and work motivation (Bakker & de Vries, 2021). Individuals experiencing burnout typically exhibit symptoms such as chronic fatigue, cynicism toward work, and decreased self-confidence (Maslach & Leiter, 2016). Gen Z employees working in service sectors such as tourism face a higher risk of burnout due to perfectionist tendencies, pressure to perform optimally, and continuous exposure to technology that may disrupt work–life balance (Putri & Wibawa, 2022).

To mitigate the negative impacts of burnout, individuals require appropriate coping strategies (Agustiningsih, 2019). Coping strategies refer to the methods or mechanisms individuals use to manage stress, either by addressing the source of stress or by regulating emotional responses (Lazarus & Folkman, in Agustiningsih, 2019). Two primary types of coping strategies are problem-focused coping, which targets the direct resolution of stressors, and emotion-focused coping, which emphasizes managing emotional responses to stress (Agustiningsih, 2019). Previous studies have extensively examined burnout. For example, research by Richadatul Aisy et al. (2023), titled “Implementation of Employee Welfare Policies for Gen Z to Address Burnout in the Workplace,” found that burnout adversely affects mental health and employee performance and proposed welfare policies to mitigate the condition. Another study by Fahri Fhauzan and Ali (2024), titled “The Influence of Workload and Burnout on Employee Performance Through Work Stress,” concluded that high workload and burnout significantly contribute to decreased

employee performance through increased work stress. Both studies highlight the crucial role of organizations in creating supportive work environments that reduce work pressure. However, research specifically addressing burnout among Gen Z in Indonesia's tourism sector particularly in Bali remains limited, creating a research gap that this study aims to address. This study focuses on Generation Z workers, who possess unique expectations and work attitudes, within the tourism sector, which is characterized by highly dynamic working conditions, especially during holiday seasons. The research not only provides an overview of burnout but also proposes stress-management strategies relevant to Gen Z characteristics. Practically, the findings are expected to offer insights for tourism management in formulating human resource policies that are more responsive to the needs of younger workers. The study also contributes theoretically to the development of human resource management literature, particularly in examining and addressing psychosocial issues such as work stress and burnout based on generational characteristics. The objective of this study is to identify the factors that cause burnout among Gen Z workers and to analyze effective strategies for managing their work stress. Accordingly, the main research questions are: What factors influence the emergence of burnout among Gen Z workers in the tourism sector, and what strategies are most effective in addressing their work-related stress? Through an in-depth qualitative approach, this study is expected to provide a comprehensive understanding of the burnout phenomenon and formulate measures to mitigate work stress among Generation Z.

METHOD

This study employs a qualitative design with an exploratory case study approach to gain an in-depth understanding of Generation Z workers' subjective experiences of burnout and their coping strategies in dealing with work-related stress during the high season in the tourism sector, with the research conducted at D'Carik Villas Ubud, Bali. Data were collected through structured and unstructured interviews as well as operational documentation, including work schedules, attendance records, and visitor data, obtained from purposively selected informants comprising Generation Z employees, co-workers, and supervisors (HRM). The primary instrument was an interview guide covering perceptions of burnout, factors contributing to work stress, and stress management strategies. Data analysis followed the model proposed by Matthew B. Miles et al. (2014), involving stages of data collection, data condensation (selection, focusing, summarizing, and simplification), data display, and conclusion drawing and verification. Data credibility was ensured through source and technique triangulation by comparing information from multiple informants and integrating interview findings with documentation, thereby producing credible insights into the phenomenon of burnout and stress management efforts among Generation Z workers within a high-pressure work environment.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Factors Causing Work Stress Influencing Burnout Among Generation Z Employees at D'Carik Villas Ubud

Burnout can occur as a result of workloads that exceed employees' personal capacities, causing them to experience work-related stress. This stress arises from employees' unpreparedness to face various job demands and the changes occurring in their work environment. Each work unit has different stressors. Overall, the factors causing work stress can be identified based on the researcher's interviews with informants as follows.

1. Task Demands

Employees at D'Carik Villas Ubud are required to meet performance targets, which are reflected in the monthly room occupancy rate throughout the year. Higher occupancy rates lead to higher revenue; therefore, the company demands that employees perform optimally, both in marketing efforts to attract guests and in improving service quality to encourage repeat visits whenever guests travel to Bali. However, each employee faces distinct challenges in meeting these demands. During the high season, task demands increase significantly compared to the low season. This increase is reflected in the number of rooms to be cleaned, the frequency of guest interactions, and the volume of special requests

that must be fulfilled within limited timeframes. Employees across divisions—such as Front Office, Housekeeping, and Marketing—experience additional workloads requiring multitasking, including rapid guest handling and cross-departmental coordination. This situation causes employees, particularly Gen Z workers, to feel more quickly fatigued and pressured, despite their efforts to maintain excellent service quality. Supporting documentation and informant testimony indicate that villa bookings are nearly fully occupied during high season, creating clear differences in job demands between low and high seasons. The 2024 occupancy data show that the villa reached 79% occupancy in July and increased to 83% in December, indicating a rise in guest volume that corresponds with increased task demands and workload. Workload intensifies significantly during high season. Informants N1, N2, and N3 reported working under limited time and high pressure due to the sharp increase in occupancy. Employees are required to deliver fast and professional service despite handling large numbers of guests, resulting in physical fatigue, reduced rest time, and decreased work concentration. These findings align with Apriana et al. (2021) and Fahrulan Fahri & Ali (2024), who state that excessive workload and time pressure increase work stress and reduce performance. Aisy et al. (2023) also note that individuals working under high-pressure conditions are vulnerable to emotional exhaustion and performance decline, especially younger workers still adapting to workplace demands. Thus, the excessive workload experienced by employees at D'Carik Villas Ubud represents organizational stress stemming from task demands.

2. Role Demands

Employees are expected to perform according to their respective duties in compliance with established SOPs. However, during high season, the surge in guest arrivals substantially increases the volume of work compared to normal periods. Due to limited staffing—particularly in housekeeping and front office divisions that interact directly with guests—employees are often required to perform multiple roles. In addition, work facilities and equipment are sometimes insufficient relative to service demands, such as limited cleaning supplies. This condition disrupts workflow efficiency, causing tasks that should be completed within a single shift to be continued by the next shift. Consequently, employees face heavier workloads, as they must meet service standards while still delivering the best possible guest experience under pressure. Informants indicated that role demands during high season differ markedly from low season conditions. Employees must work faster, multitask, and coordinate across divisions due to increased guest numbers. Limited staffing and supporting facilities further intensify the situation, requiring divisions to support one another because of high booking volumes and insufficient staff per shift. This often delays task completion and results in employees assuming dual roles. Non-Gen Z coworkers, who generally possess longer work experience, provide more objective assessments of Gen Z employees' ability to handle dual roles and increased demands. During high season, staff frequently experience double job descriptions due to limited manpower for example, housekeeping staff assisting front office operations during guest surges and marketing staff coordinating room reservations. This overlap creates imbalanced responsibilities and pressure from role conflict. According to Robbins, role ambiguity and role overload significantly increase work stress. Dhaniawari & Sudarince (2024) similarly found that mismatches between job roles and individual capacity particularly among Gen Z workers are a primary cause of burnout. At D'Carik Villas Ubud, limited staffing results in responsibilities that exceed available resources, placing employees under substantial pressure to meet service standards.

3. Interpersonal Demands

Working during high season also creates interpersonal pressure. The rapid increase in guest numbers is not always matched by adequate resources and facilities, leading to friction among employees, particularly when coordinating the use of limited equipment. Employees must complete tasks quickly according to service standards, and competition for facilities can trigger minor conflicts. Informants reported that workplace dynamics during high season often make relationships more tense compared to low season periods.

Interpersonal conflicts are primarily driven by miscommunication and work fatigue. Increased workload, limited facilities, and urgent service demands disrupt communication, causing misunderstandings in task distribution and resource usage. Negative feedback during interactions and inadequate tools further contribute to interpersonal conflict and reduced work effectiveness. Informants N1, N2, and N3 reported frequent minor tensions due to miscommunication and high pressure, with employees becoming more sensitive and easily offended, especially when fatigued or competing for limited equipment. This indicates communication breakdowns and decreased empathy among team members. Robbins (2015) states that interpersonal conflict generates psychological stress by disrupting individuals' social balance. Putri & Wibawa (2022) further note that social pressure, intensive digital interaction, and expectations of constant responsiveness exacerbate stress and burnout among Gen Z. Therefore, strained interpersonal relationships at D'Carik Villas Ubud reinforce organizational factors as sources of work stress.

4. Organizational Structure

Employees must also adapt to a simple organizational structure with limited human resources. During high season, they are required to adapt quickly and assume roles beyond their primary job descriptions, often causing discomfort due to staffing and facility constraints. Interviews indicate that the villa's relatively small organizational structure directly contributes to work stress among Gen Z employees. Although task allocation is generally clear, limited staff numbers force employees to assume additional roles, sometimes causing confusion about priorities. However, the small structure also provides flexibility for direct communication with supervisors and opportunities for cross-functional learning. Overall, this situation creates multitasking challenges that generate stress because responsibilities are not proportional to available manpower. The structure presents both advantages and disadvantages: employees gain development opportunities through diverse roles and open communication, yet limited resources and increased workload during high season become major stressors. Employees reported needing to make independent decisions in urgent situations due to unclear boundaries of responsibility, which further increases stress. Robbins emphasizes that unstable or poorly defined organizational structures create uncertainty that triggers stress. Aisy et al. (2023) similarly note that small organizations with immature structures are prone to work pressure due to imbalanced authority and responsibilities. Afifah et al. (2024) add that organizations must manage time allocation and work balance to prevent stress caused by disproportionate workload distribution.

5. Organizational Leadership

Leadership plays a crucial role in maintaining operational continuity despite limited staff. Leaders act not only as directors but also as facilitators who encourage flexibility and multi-role performance. During high season, leadership provides motivation that helps Gen Z employees feel more confident. However, frequently changing instructions can create confusion and anxiety about making mistakes, thereby increasing stress. Employees reported feeling more comfortable when supervisors regularly check on field conditions, and sharing sessions help reduce tension and foster open communication. Nevertheless, overly laissez-faire leadership is perceived as less effective, as Gen Z workers still require clear guidance. Leadership at the villa is generally open and communicative, with HR managers and owners often directly assisting employees during busy periods, boosting morale and appreciation. However, sudden changes in instructions create pressure for employees who must make rapid decisions. Robbins notes that inconsistent leadership styles increase stress due to uncertainty. Rahman & Dewi (2023) emphasize the importance of empathetic leadership in reducing stress, while Aura & Sitorus (2025) highlight that flexible policies and supportive leadership maintain psychological balance and productivity. In this context, moral support from leaders serves as a protective factor for Gen Z employees under high pressure.

6. Organizational Life Cycle

Organizations evolve through stages from establishment to growth, maturity, and eventual decline each creating distinct pressures for employees. As a relatively small villa, D'Carik Villas Ubud is currently in the growth stage. Increasing service demand reflects organizational expansion but also introduces

challenges typical of developing organizations. Employees experience stress from the need to deliver fast and accurate service amid sharply increased workloads, potential interdepartmental miscommunication, and guest expectations for immediate service. Informants indicated that the villa is still recovering and expanding after the pandemic, with high guest numbers during peak seasons requiring employees to work more quickly and efficiently. This growth generates pressures such as heavy workloads, communication challenges, and demands for optimal service. Although adjustments are ongoing, the organization is gradually moving toward more stable and professional operations. Robbins (2015) explains that growth stages are characterized by uncertainty, rapid change, and significant workload increases. This aligns with informants' statements that guest numbers have surged while staffing remains limited, forcing employees to handle multiple responsibilities. Studies by Alisy et al. (2023) and Afifah et al. (2024) also indicate that developing organizations require structural support and stress-management training to prevent employee burnout during expansion.

Burnout Phenomenon

High job demands can lead to burnout among human resources, both mentally and physically. Individuals experiencing burnout often feel exhausted, bored, and unable to cope with work pressure, resulting in negative impacts on organizational operations.

1. Physical Exhaustion

Physical exhaustion is one of the most visible forms of fatigue experienced by employees, particularly during the high season when workload increases drastically and working hours become longer than usual. This condition triggers excessive tiredness, decreased energy, and difficulty maintaining concentration at work. Physical exhaustion is a major impact experienced by Generation Z employees in the villa work environment during the high season. The sharp increase in workload leads to longer working hours and high physical activity, such as cleaning rooms or serving guests without sufficient rest. This condition results in excessive fatigue, muscle soreness, reduced energy, difficulty concentrating, and psychological pressure due to dual workloads. Nevertheless, employees are still required to remain friendly and professional in front of guests, which further exacerbates their fatigue. This indicates that high job demands without adequate rest balance can trigger burnout among young employees.

2. Emotional Exhaustion

Another form of burnout experienced by Gen Z employees is emotional exhaustion. This condition arises when individuals feel mentally drained due to continuous work pressure, high service demands toward guests, and dense working conditions during the high season. Employees begin to lose motivation, become easily irritated, and have difficulty regulating their emotions at work. Emotional exhaustion becomes one of the dominant forms of burnout among Gen Z employees during the high season. Employees tend to become short-tempered, easily offended, and inclined to withdraw from social interactions outside of work. This reflects a decline in emotional stability due to accumulated fatigue. When emotional energy is depleted, employees become less enthusiastic and struggle to maintain professionalism in delivering services. This demonstrates that an imbalance between workload and psychological needs can worsen burnout symptoms and reduce employee performance quality.

3. Mental Exhaustion

In addition to physical fatigue, employees also experience mental exhaustion. This condition results from continuous work pressure, high service demands, and insufficient rest, leading to feelings of boredom, cynicism toward coworkers, and difficulty concentrating. Mental exhaustion affects not only emotional conditions but also employees' ability to think clearly and maintain interpersonal relationships at work. Difficulty concentrating and the emergence of cynical attitudes indicate that individuals are beginning to lose control over accumulated stress. In the hospitality industry context, such as at D'Carik Villas Ubud, this poses a serious challenge because service quality heavily depends on emotional stability and coordination among employees.

4. Low Personal Accomplishment

Another form of burnout experienced by employees is a diminished sense of personal accomplishment. This condition occurs when employees feel that their efforts and performance do not yield results proportional to the work they have invested. Feelings of being undervalued, lack of appreciation, and limited opportunities for development cause employees to lose pride in their work. The absence of recognition in the workplace can reduce employees' confidence in performing tasks and diminish their work motivation, leading to boredom at work, as expressed by one employee. Boredom is not only caused by heavy workloads but also by unmet emotional needs for recognition. When appreciation is lacking, employees tend to feel that their efforts are meaningless. In a high-paced work environment such as D'Carik Villas Ubud, simple forms of appreciation—such as praise or expressions of gratitude—play an important role in maintaining motivation and a sense of belonging toward one's job. The burnout phenomenon among Generation Z employees at D'Carik Villas Ubud is a direct consequence of work stress originating from organizational factors during the high season. Burnout manifests in the form of physical, emotional, and mental exhaustion, as well as a low sense of personal achievement. High job demands, dual roles, long working hours, and pressure to maintain service quality are the primary triggers of burnout. This phenomenon is further reinforced by the characteristics of Generation Z, who tend to have high sensitivity to mental health issues and a strong need for work–life balance. When these expectations are unmet, prolonged work pressure can easily develop into burnout. Therefore, burnout should not be viewed merely as an individual weakness but as a signal of imbalance between job demands and organizational support. The burnout phenomenon identified among Gen Z employees at D'Carik Villas Ubud indicates that high work pressure during the high season affects their performance. Burnout is a reaction to chronic work stress resulting from an imbalance between job demands and individual capacity. The findings show that all four forms of exhaustion physical, mental, emotional, and low personal accomplishment occur simultaneously and are interrelated. These results support the study by Fauzhan Fahri & Ali (2024), which explains that excessive workload often becomes a source of work stress leading to burnout, defined as physical, mental, and emotional exhaustion due to prolonged job pressure. Additionally, research by Dhaniswari & Sudarnice (2024) indicates that burnout can negatively affect employee performance and is influenced by stress-causing factors. When high workloads are not balanced with adequate social support and recognition, employees tend to experience decreased energy, loss of enthusiasm, and ultimately job dissatisfaction.

Strategies for Overcoming Work Stress

Various factors causing work stress during the high season can be addressed adaptively and effectively by Generation Z employees at D'Carik Villas Ubud. Each employee also employs different efforts to cope with workplace stress. Several work stress issues described above have been successfully managed by the employees. This study identifies three main methods used by Generation Z workers at D'Carik Villas Ubud to cope with work stress during the high season, namely social support, self-evaluation, and self-healing. These three methods are applied flexibly and complement one another, adjusted to working conditions, individual capacity, and the level of pressure experienced. Statements from the first, second, and third informants are presented as follows:

1. Social Support Method

Social support is the coping strategy most frequently used by Gen Z workers in dealing with work stress. This support is obtained from both colleagues and supervisors. In a busy and high-pressure work environment, the presence of coworkers who help and understand one another provides a sense of security and reduces psychological burden. Gen Z workers tend to share stories, complaints, and work experiences with colleagues within or across divisions as a form of emotion-focused coping.

The social support method is manifested through providing motivation individually and collectively, as well as mutual assistance among employees at work. When supervisors demonstrate empathy and appreciation, Gen Z workers feel more valued and motivated to endure work pressure. Supportive

working relationships, open communication, and empathy from supervisors and colleagues can reduce the emotional strain experienced by Gen Z workers. When employees feel heard and appreciated, heavy workloads can be perceived as shared challenges rather than individual pressure. This indicates that organizations have a strategic role in creating a psychologically safe work environment.

2. Self-Calming / Self-Healing Method

The second strategy used by Gen Z workers is self-healing as a form of emotion-based stress management. Self-healing is carried out through various relaxation activities, such as getting sufficient rest, listening to music, enjoying leisure time, engaging in hobbies, and limiting work-related interactions outside working hours. The self-healing method helps create positive feelings related to the recovery of physical and emotional energy among Gen Z workers and enhances self-satisfaction, preventing them from being entirely focused on work pressure. Relaxation activities and self-reward practices help maintain a balance between job demands and personal needs. Overall, the implementation of self-healing indicates that Gen Z workers possess relatively high awareness of the importance of maintaining mental health.

3. Self-Evaluation Method

The third method used by Gen Z workers is self-evaluation. This involves reflecting on one's abilities, personal limitations, and performance achievements during work. Under increasing work stress, Gen Z workers attempt to adjust their expectations of themselves to avoid excessive perfectionism. Self-evaluation encourages adaptive attitudes, where workers focus more on the process and effort rather than solely on outcomes. Thus, self-evaluation plays an important role in maintaining psychological balance and preventing work stress from escalating into more severe burnout. Gen Z employees cope by prioritizing main tasks and completing them gradually. If a task has an imminent deadline, it is handled first. When employees are unable to manage multiple tasks simultaneously, other employees even from different divisions—are willing to assist. Informant N6, who serves as HRM, stated that managing communication and time management is also an important strategy for addressing work stress. From an individual perspective, Gen Z employees apply simple self-healing strategies such as deep breathing, listening to music, or engaging in hobbies as relaxation techniques to calm the mind and maintain emotional balance. These activities help reduce emotional tension, maintain focus, and restore work motivation. Additionally, management plays a crucial role through communication and time-management training, as well as an open approach that allows employees to feel heard and prevents them from becoming trapped in burnout conditions. The findings of this study support research by Aura & Sitorus (2025), which shows that burnout can be reduced through effective stress management, supportive work environments, and flexible work policies. Afifah et al. (2024) also state that self-healing methods can serve as effective approaches to reducing stress, including listening to music, meditation, exercise, and engaging in hobbies. With appropriate strategies, individuals, organizations, and governments can collaborate to create workplace well-being and improve employee productivity.

Analysis of Work Stress Coping Strategies Among Generation Z Employees at D'Carik Villas Ubud

Based on the interviews conducted by the researcher, Generation Z employees tend to experience work-related stress. This condition was reported by several key informants (N1, N2, and N3), whose ages range from 20 to 25 years. They acknowledged that the stress they experienced was primarily caused by overwork during the high season, including working beyond their formal job descriptions and assuming additional responsibilities from other divisions. As reflected in the data presented by each informant, employees at D'Carik Villas Ubud employ their own strategies to cope with work-related stress. Coping strategies refer to recovery mechanisms from stress or physical and psychological reactions characterized by discomfort, unease, or pressure. Based on Generation Z employees' efforts to manage work stress during the high season, this study finds alignment with three of the four methods proposed by Anwar Prabu Mangkunegara (cited in Shandy et al., 2013), which state that work stress can be addressed through four approaches:

1. Social support method, demonstrated through individual and team motivation, discussions with colleagues, and mutual assistance among employees.
2. Self-calming method, reflected in employees' efforts to maintain positive thinking, accept demanding conditions as challenges for both individuals and the organization, and engage in self-healing activities such as listening to music, pursuing hobbies, and enjoying nature or open environments.
3. Biofeedback method, which was not utilized because the stress experienced by Generation Z employees did not exhibit symptoms requiring professional assistance or consultation from specialists such as doctors or psychiatrists.
4. Self-evaluation method, conducted before, during, and after completing work tasks. Employees strive to align performance, responsibilities, and time constraints during the high season, while also discussing work outcomes and seeking feedback and solutions from colleagues and supervisors.

At D'Carik Villas Ubud, work stress management during the high season relies on three of Mangkunegara's methods social support, self-calming, and self-evaluation. This indicates that work stress during peak periods can be effectively mitigated through these approaches, preventing significant negative consequences; therefore, the biofeedback method (professional assistance) is not considered necessary. In addition, supervisors consistently foster a positive work environment, enabling stress to be managed effectively and supporting the maintenance of positive employee performance.

CONCLUSION

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion, several conclusions can be drawn as follows: The factors causing work stress among Generation Z employees at D'Carik Villas Ubud arise from several triggering conditions. These include increased job demands related to the frequency of employee interactions with guests, numerous special requests that must be fulfilled within a short time, and additional workload requiring multitasking abilities. Role demands on Gen Z employees require them to work faster, particularly due to the surge in bookings during the high season and limited staffing within a single shift. This situation compels employees to perform multiple roles (double job descriptions) and provide cross-support across divisions. The demand for rapid service often disrupts communication among employees, leading to misunderstandings in task allocation and the use of work facilities. The relatively small organizational structure directly contributes to the emergence of work stress among Gen Z employees; however, it also provides flexibility for direct communication with supervisors. Frequently changing instructions from management create confusion and additional pressure for employees who must make quick decisions. Furthermore, the organization is in a developmental stage, characterized by increasing guest numbers and operational expansion, yet without a fully stable work system.

Strategies to cope with work stress during the high season at D'Carik Villas Ubud are directed at addressing the identified stressors through three primary methods. First, social support methods involve sharing experiences, listening to colleagues, and providing work motivation. Second, self-calming methods (self-healing) include relaxing the mind, engaging in hobbies, listening to music, and enjoying nature. Third, self-evaluation methods involve maintaining work notes before, during, and after work, as well as seeking feedback from colleagues regarding performance. These findings indicate that work stress during the high season can be effectively managed through these three approaches, preventing significant negative outcomes; therefore, biofeedback methods (professional expert assistance) were not deemed necessary. In addition, supervisors consistently strive to maintain a positive work environment, enabling stress to be managed effectively and to produce positive performance outcomes.

Recommendation

1. Recommendations for Management (More Concise)

Work stress among Gen Z employees is driven by overlapping task, role, and interpersonal demands, especially during high season, resulting in heavier workloads, double job roles, and miscommunication. Management should build a supportive communication culture through regular briefings and

evaluations, and consider hiring daily workers during peak periods to reduce overload. Small organizational structures often cause task overlap and unclear coordination. Therefore, simple SOPs covering core operations and coordination are needed to provide clarity, job certainty, and reduce burnout risk, supported by training to enhance initiative and flexibility. Burnout symptoms—physical, emotional, mental exhaustion, and reduced personal accomplishment—can be addressed through balanced schedules, rest time, empathetic communication, open discussion spaces, recognition, and team-building. Additional well-being support such as relaxation activities, controlled gadget use, and journaling can also help employees manage stress.

2. Recommendations for Management of D'Carik Villas Ubud

Employees have generally managed stress well during high season despite pressures and limited facilities. However, management should strengthen social support through open communication, short briefings before or after shifts, accessible supervisors, and adequate work facilities during peak periods to improve productivity and financial performance. Appreciation can be given through overtime bonuses, verbal recognition, rotating leave after high season, or flexible hours. Controlled use of gadgets and music may support focus, mood, coordination, comfort, and reduce boredom that could lead to burnout.

3. Recommendations for Gen Z Employees

Gen Z employees should continue optimizing self-regulation strategies such as breathing techniques, emotional control, mindfulness, and short breaks to maintain professionalism and performance. Self-evaluation and work–life balance through exercise, recreation, and hobbies can also reduce stress. They are encouraged to communicate proactively with supervisors about work obstacles or emotional pressure so that timely support can be provided.

4. Recommendations for Future Research

Future studies should apply mixed-methods approaches to obtain more comprehensive data on stress levels and influencing factors, and examine broader tourism-sector samples for comparison. Including additional variables such as organizational culture, workload, and communication patterns may deepen understanding of factors affecting work stress among younger employees. These recommendations aim to contribute to creating healthier, more supportive, and adaptive workplaces for younger generations.

REFERENCES

- Afifah, N. , Ramadhan, I. , & Syafitri, D. (2024). Strategi Organisasi dalam Menanggulangi Burnout Karyawan: Pendekatan Holistik di Era Digital. *Jurnal Manajemen Dan Organisasi*, 5(1), 60–70.
- Agarwal, A., & Vaghela, P. (2019). Managing Gen Z workforce: A strategic HR perspective. *Journal of Human Resources and Sustainability*.
- Agustiningasih, N. (2019). Gambaran Stress Akademik dan Strategi Koping Pada Mahasiswa Keperawatan. *Jurnal Ners Dan Kebidanan (Journal of Ners and Midwifery)*, 6(2), 241–250. <https://doi.org/10.26699/jnk.v6i2.art.p241-250>
- Aisy, R. , Ghifary, M. T. , & Laksmi, D. R. (2023). Implementasi kebijakan kesejahteraan karyawan Gen Z dalam menanggulangi burnout di lingkungan kerja. *Musytari: Jurnal Manajemen, Akuntansi, Dan Ekonomi*, 71–80. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.8734/musytari.v1i12.762>
- Andayani. (2023). *Self healing sebagai strategi pengelolaan stres*. . Surabaya: Cakrawala Press.
- Antonius. (2020). *Beban kerja dan stres kerja*. Pasuruan: CV. Penerbit Kiara Media.
- Apriana, I. W. A., Edris, M., & Sutono. (2021). Pengaruh Beban Kerja dan Burnout Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai dengan Kepuasan Kerja sebagai Variabel Intervening (Studi Kasus pada Pegawai Dinas Pemberdayaan Masyarakat dan Desa Kabupaten Rembang). *Jurnal Studi Manajemen Bisnis*, 1(1).
- Aryawan, P. K. D., & Diniari, N. K. S. (2020). Gambaran stresor dan koping stres dalam proses penyelesaian skripsi pada mahasiswa Fakultas Kedokteran Universitas Udayana tahun 2016. *Jurnal Medika Udayana*, 9(9), 87–92.

EXPLORATION OF BURNOUT PHENOMENA AND COPING STRATEGIES FOR WORK-RELATED STRESS AMONG GENERATION Z

Ni Putu Shintania Pramesti and Luh Putu Mahyuni

- Aura, A. , & Sitorus, J. (2025). Kebijakan Kerja Fleksibel dan Lingkungan Suportif dalam Menjaga Kesehatan Mental Gen Z. *Urnal Ilmiah Manajemen, Ekonomi, & Akuntansi (MEA)*, 8(3), 3049–3056
- Ayu, I. G. A. M., Wibawa, I. M. A., & Wijaya, I. M. A. P. (2021). Hubungan Antara Workload dan Burnout pada Karyawan di Surabaya dengan Effort-Reward Imbalance sebagai Variabel Moderator. *Jurnal Ilmu Psikologi Dan Kesehatan*, 1(4), 181–190.
- Azhar, Y. , Wibowo, A. , & Kurniawati, R. (2021). Burnout pada tenaga kesehatan selama masa pandemi. *PsikoNeo: Jurnal Psikologi Neo*, 3(1), 1–9
- Badri, I. A. (2020). Hubungan Beban Kerja Dan Lingkungan Kerja Dengan Stres Kerja Perawat Ruangan Icu Dan Igd. *Human Care Journal*, 5(1), 379. <https://doi.org/10.32883/hcj.v5i1.730>
- Bakker, A. B. , & de Vries, J. D. (2021). Burnout and work engagement: The JD-R approach. *Annual Review of Organizational Psychology and Organizational Behavior*, 8(1), 389–411.
- Bambang Septiawan, Endah Masrunik, & M. Rizal. (2020). *Motivasi Kerja dan Generasi Z: Teori dan Penerapan*. Zaida Digital Publishing.
- Baron, R. A. , & Greenberg, J. (2003). *Behavior in organizations* (8th ed.). . Prentice Hall. BPS Provinsi Bali. (2025). Perkembangan pariwisata Provinsi Bali Desember 2024. <https://bali.bps.go.id/id/pressrelease/2025/02/03/717939/perkembangan-pariwisata-provinsi-bali-desember-2024.html>
- Dhaniswari, N. M. P. , & Sudarnice. (2024). Pengaruh work-life balance dan burnout terhadap kinerja karyawan Gen Z di Kota Denpasar. *ASSET: Jurnal Manajemen Dan Bisnis*, 7(1) , 53–62.
- Fahri Fhauzan, R., & Ali, H. (2024). Pengaruh Beban Kerja dan Burnout Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Melalui Stress Kerja. *Jurnal Pendidikan Siber Nusantara*, 2(4), 169–176. <https://doi.org/10.38035/jpsn.v2i4.290>
- Folkman, S. , & Moskowitz, J. T. (2004). Coping : Pitfalls and promise. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 55, 745–774.
- GoodStats. (2023). Ini sederet alasan terpopuler menurut Gen Z ketika ingin resign. https://goodstats.id/article/ini-sederet-alasan-terpopuler-menurut-gen-z-ketika-ingin-resign-iepME?utm_source=chatgpt.com
- Handoko, T. H. (2011). *Manajemen Personalia dan Sumber Daya Manusia*. Yogyakarta: BPFE.
- Hansez, I., Schins, F., & Rollin, F. (2019). Occupational burnout: Symptoms and consequences. *International Journal of Occupational Safety and Ergonomics*, 25(1), 123–131.
- Hasbillah, M. S. R. , & Rahmasari, D. (2022). Burnout akademik pada mahasiswa yang sedang menempuh tugas akhir. *Jurnal Penelitian Musytari*, 1(12), 122–132.
- Hastini, L. Y., Fahmi, R., & Lukito, H. (2020). Apakah Pembelajaran Menggunakan Teknologi dapat Meningkatkan Literasi Manusia pada Generasi Z di Indonesia? *Jurnal Manajemen Informatika (JAMIKA)*, 10(1), 12–28. <https://doi.org/10.34010/jamika.v10i1.2678>
- Lestari, A. , & Handoko, T. (2021). Kelelahan Digital: Dampak Penggunaan Teknologi Intensif terhadap Burnout pada Karyawan. *Jurnal Psikologi Dan Teknologi*, 3(2), 45–55.
- Li-li, Z. , & Ma, L. (2024). Social psychology characteristics of Generation Z. *Journal of Modern Youth Psychology*, 6(1), 15–22.
- Lumban Gaol, N. T. (2016). Teori Stres: Stimulus, Respons, dan Transaksional. *Buletin Psikologi*, 24(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.22146/bpsi.11224>
- Maslach, C., & Leiter, M. P. (2016). Burnout and engagement: Contributions to a new vision. *Burnout Research*, 5(1), 55–63.
- Mentari, A. Z. B., Liana, E., & Pristya, T. Y. R. (2020). Teknik Manajemen Stres yang Paling Efektif pada Remaja: Literature Review. *JURNAL ILMIAH KESEHATAN MASYARAKAT : Media Komunikasi Komunitas Kesehatan Masyarakat*, 12(4), 191–196. <https://doi.org/10.52022/jikm.v12i4.69>
- Miles, M. B., Huberman, A. M., & Saldana, J. (2014). *Qualitative Data Analysis, A Methods Sourcebook* (edition 3). Sage Publications.

EXPLORATION OF BURNOUT PHENOMENA AND COPING STRATEGIES FOR WORK-RELATED STRESS AMONG GENERATION Z

Ni Putu Shintania Pramesti and Luh Putu Mahyuni

- Nadiasari, E., & Palma, D. I. (2022). Membelajarkan Kemampuan Berpikir Kritis Matematis pada Generasi Z. *Seminar Nasional Pendidikan Matematika*, 3(2), 175–184.
- Nur'aini, R. D. (2020). Penerapan Metode Studi Kasus Yin Dalam Penelitian Arsitektur Dan Perilaku. *INERSIA: LNformasi Dan Ekspose Hasil Riset Teknik Sipil Dan Arsitektur*, 16(1), 92–104. <https://doi.org/10.21831/inersia.v16i1.31319>
- Putri, A. A. R. , & Wibawa, I. B. N. (2022). engaruh burnout terhadap produktivitas Generasi Z pada mahasiswa Universitas Bhayangkara Jakarta Raya. *Musytari Neraca: Jurnal Manajemen, Akuntansi, Dan Ekonomi*, 1(12), 71–80.
- Rahman, A. , & Dewi, S. (2023). Strategi personal dalam mengurangi stres kerja. *Innovative: Journal of Social Science Research*, 3(3), 45–52.
- Retnowati, S. , Laksmi, R., & Hartono, A. (2023). Fenomena burnout pada pekerja generasi Z: Kajian psikologis. *Jurnal Psikologi Kerja*, 15(1), 33–47.
- Richadatul Aisy, M., Tahajuddi Ghifary, & Dwi Laksmi R. (2023). Implementasi Kebijakan Kesejahteraan Karyawan Gen Z dalam Menanggulangi Burnout di Lingkungan Kerja. *Musytari: Jurnal Manajemen, Akuntansi, Dan Ekonomi*, 12(1), 71–80.
- Riedl, R. , & Thomas, R. J. (2019). Psychological stress and burnout in IT professionals. *Information Systems Journal*, 29(6), 1240–1272.
- Robbins, S. P. (2015). *Organizational behavior* (15th ed.). . Boston: Pearson Education. Salvagioni, D. A. J. , Melanda, F. N. , Mesas, A. E. , González, A. D. , Gabani, F. L. , & Andrade, S. M. (2017). Physical, psychological and occupational consequences of job burnout: A systematic review of prospective studies. *PLOS ONE*, 12(10).
- Sari, I. P. , Ifdil, I. , & Yendi, F. M. (2020). Konsep nomophobia pada remaja generasi Z. *Jurnal Riset Tindakan*, 1(1), 10–19.
- Siregar, I. M. (2024). Manajemen Stres Strategi Menghadapi Tekanan Hidup. *Psikologi*, 1(4), 1–15.
- Suartana, P. (2020). *Stres kerja dan dampaknya terhadap kinerja*. Denpasar: Pustaka Bali.
- Yakup. (2019). Kontribusi Sektor Pariwisata terhadap Ekonomi Nasional. *Jurnal Ekonomi dan Pariwisata*.